

A Quality of Experience Evaluation of an Interactive Multisensory 2.5D Virtual Reality Art Exhibit

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Abstract

In recent years, museums have become more interactive and immersive through the adaptation of technology within large scale art exhibitions. Due to these changes, these new types of cultural experiences are more appealing to younger audiences. Despite these positive changes, some museum experiences are still primarily focused on visual art experiences. These remain out of reach to those with visual impairments. Such unimodal and visual dominated experiences restrict these users who depend on sensory feedback to experience the world around them. In this paper, the authors propose a novel VR experience which incorporates multisensory technologies. It allows individuals to engage and interact with a visual artwork museum experience presented as a fully immersive VR environment. Users can interact with virtual paintings and trigger sensory zones which deliver multisensory feedback to the user. These sensory zones are unique to each painting, presenting thematic audio and smells, custom haptic feedback to feel the artwork, and lastly air, light and thermal changes in an effort to engage those with visual impairments.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Visual Impairment, Multisensory, Accessibility, Immersive Experience

1 Introduction

There are many etiquettes which must be considered when attending a modern-day museum. Some examples include minimizing noise and avoiding flash photography, but most important of all to not touch the items which are on display. This etiquette is essential to the preservation of paintings and artifacts. However, this also limits the ability of those with visual impairments to experience visual art. In recent years, museums have begun to explore new and emerging technologies to present visual art which can be touched [1] [2] [3], with a prime objective of making the experiences more accessible to those with visual impairments.

Visual impairments are disorders which can affect an individual's ability to see or interpret visual information. There are numerous forms of visual impairments which can affect how people perceive the world. Some common problems range from challenges with blurred vision, sensitivity to light, and difficulties seeing at night. According to [4], cataracts is the leading cause of blindness and the second leading cause of moderate and severe visual impairment. Cataracts are primarily age related; however, they can occur as a result of injury to the tissue which makes up the eyes lens. Individuals who experience symptoms of cataracts are limited in how they engage with leisure activities such as visiting cinemas, theatres, and museums. Cataracts and other visual impairments affect not only how people see but can also play into other aspects of general life.

Throughout history, there have been many artists who have thrived whilst experiencing a visual impairment, examples of such include Claude Monet (cataracts) [5], Leonardo da Vinci (intermittent exotropia) [6], and Francis Bacon (dysmorphopsia) [7]. Despite these limitations, these influential artists continued their journey within the creative community and inspired generations. Although artists can develop methods to assist with the creative aspect of art, the consumption of art is still somewhat effected. As a visual impairment evolves, individuals often become more dependent on their sensory system to engage with the world around them [8]. The additional senses become more important as people depend more on touch, smell, and auditory experiences as a primary method of

understanding the world around them.

As technology has evolved, collections of art have transformed from the presentation of 2D canvas within museums to fully interactive media experiences utilizing projection-based media [9], or immersive technologies. Newer technologies such as touch-screen tablets and mobile phones include accessibility features to assist those with visual impairments. This includes a level of customization to increase font size alter the appearance of colours, provide access to magnification tools, and in some cases provide text-to-speech systems which guide users around an interface. Although this form of accessibility is sufficient for 2D media experiences, next generation and fully immersive technologies (Virtual, Mixed, and Augmented Reality) provide new challenges for inclusivity.

Traditionally, game development has focused on the creation of two dimensional (2D) or three dimensional (3D) graphical worlds to immersive users. 2D games are generated using collections of image planes which have been layered in the X and Y axis, the players view perspective is then limited to one axis. Meanwhile 3D games utilize advanced graphical processing and allow the player to perceive a world in three dimensions (X, Y, and Z), players are free to roam the world without view restrictions. Although traditionally consumed using monitors, advances in technology now allow 3D games to be presented in virtual reality (VR) further immersing the user into a fully simulated virtual world. Despite these advances in recent years, developers have begun to experiment with a new style of graphical rendering known as 2.5D (2.5 dimensional).

In 2.5D, flat 2D image planes and 3D elements are mixed and layered to allow players to gain more depth and immersion throughout gameplay. In this context, this paper presents a work in progress design and development of an accessible multimodal VR museum exhibit which aims to present 2.5D virtual artworks. Each layer within the 2.5D composition will coincide with sensory zones to allow those with a visual impairment to experience multimodal feedback from the works of art.

2 Related Work

Virtual reality has been explored as a tool for entertainment, education, retail, architecture, and virtual tourism. In recent years, virtual reality has also been used as a tool to assist those with visual impairments to experience the world around them. In [10], how virtual reality fostered embodied learning benefiting those with visual impairments in teaching scenarios was investigated. This is because it engages multiple senses, including proprioception, body movement, touch, and hearing, rather than focusing primarily on visual resources.

Exhibits which focus on accessibility are core to the development of new and inclusive experiences which allow those with a disability or impairment to engage with cultural galleries. In 2021, the “Blind Spot” exhibit was presented at the Central Museum in Utrecht [2]. It focused on stimulating all the senses. The exhibit presented a 4D art experience using real world objects which allowed visitors to touch, smell, and hear audio all of which were electively themed to the visual works. The primary objective of the exhibit was to make visual art more accessible for those with visual impairments. Similarly, Spain’s Prado Museum which has created 3D copies of some of the worlds most well-known visual art and made it part of the exhibit [1]. Utilizing a novel painting mixture, chemicals react to create a 3D depth to the paintings surface allowing those with a visual impairment to feel the colour and texture of the works.

Other examples of this can be seen in the work of tech startup NeuroDigital who are exploring the use of VR and haptic feedback as a mechanism to interact with sculptures on display in museums. Their exhibit titled “Touching Masterpieces”, appeared in the National Gallery of Prague. It aimed to transform physical objects into virtual objects which people could “see” using a haptic glove technology [3].

The work of [2] [1] [10] and [3] highlights the importance of stimulating the senses for individuals with visual impairments. As the ocular system degrades, a greater dependency is placed on the other 4 senses. Existing work has emphasized the importance of using audio to assist with localization [11] and present on-demand audio descriptions to improve independent access to and understanding of visual artworks [12]. Other sensory works have explored the utility of using thermal changes to convey depth and colour [13] [14]. In [15], authors presented a

Figure 1: Proposed Multisensory VR System Design

multimodal system to assist those with visual impairments to experience visual art. The process required the high-resolution scanning of images, the images were then processed to extract a heightmap which accentuated key details within the visual art. The height maps were then 3D printed utilizing special means to create tactile graphics which users could feel, this was combined with localised touch sensitive audio to trigger descriptive overviews.

3 Proposed System

The following section presents an overview of the proposed system, first the system design is presented outlining the hardware setup. Following this, the user experience section provides an overview of how the user will interact with the virtual world. Lastly, the proposed methodology for the system evaluation is presented.

3.1 System Design

The system design (**Error! Reference source not found.**) consists of three core blocks: (a) Visual art understanding and processing, (b) application development, and (c) sensory hardware.

3.1.1 Visual Art Understanding and Processing

The initial development phase will focus on the careful selection and aggregation of visual works from the famous artist Claude Monet. Paintings will be processed using image editing tools such as Adobe Photoshop to separate layers of visual information.

These layers will be processed within a 3D modelling tool such as Blender to generate the 2.5D representations. An example of this can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.** [16] which portrays Claude Monet's - Haystacks, End of Summer. In an effort to gain insight into the objective of each of the paintings, research will be carried out on a per painting basis in an effort to identify what the artist had visualized as part of the work. This process will be used to identify thematic audio for each of the paintings.

3.1.2 Application Development and Sensory Hardware

The Unity3D game engine will be utilized to develop the experience. The core of VR interaction will be implemented using the Unity XR Interaction Toolkit [17]. However, additional integration will be required on a per device basis (as outlined later in this section). The proposed application will stimulate the audio and visual senses using the Meta Quest Pro. Although this system is capable of a wireless experience, the headset will be connected to a PC in a tethered setup. This approach is required due to the number of VR accessories which are needed for the proposed system. Due to this, a PC with 32GB of RAM, an Intel i9 (K-Series), and an Nvidia RTX 3080 will be used to run the application.

A haptic glove system from MANUS has been proposed to allow users to gain a tactile sensation whilst interacting with the immersive visual art [18]. Lastly, the SENSIKS Sensory Reality Pod [19] will be utilized to

**Figure 2: Claude Monet's- "Haystacks, End of Summer" visualized in 2.5D.
Sensory zones are highlighted (a)- (d)**

generate thermal, light, and wind changes for the end user. The sensory reality pod has been selected due to the enclosed nature of the system and seated position which will serve as a measure of safety for users of the experience.

3.2 User Experience

The VR application aims to present users with a small collection of paintings from the world-renowned artist Claude Monet. Each painting will present a unique sensory response from the system. The primary objective of this is to convey the feeling and emotion inspired from the artist through an associated multisensory experience. Due to the variability of each work, the following provides an overview of the system's potential sensory feedback.

As users move their hands through the visual works, they will engage with sensory zones. An example of these sensory zones has been visualized in Figure 2 (a) – (d). These sensory zones will trigger multimodal feedback to the end user in the form of tactile, audio, olfactory, light, and airflow changes. Thematic audio will be presented, as users engage with different layers. Volume will be altered between louder and softer tones to convey depth and distance to the end user. Users will feel the depth of different artworks with haptic gloves as each layer conveys feedback alterations. Thermal changes will occur within the SENSIKS Sensory Reality Pod as users engage with different layers within the virtual painting. The correlations that exist between warm and near, cold and far will be used to convey depth and distance through temperature range. Considering already established approaches to multimedia accessibility [20], the VR experience will place an emphasis on the integration of user navigation and interaction paradigms which are cognizant of those with visual impairments. Examples of this include the use of audible cues, the presentation of haptic feedback to the user.

3.3 Assessment Methodology

As part of the evaluation process, the system will be evaluated utilizing two independent groups. The initial group will focus on those without any visual impairments in an effort to gain insight into the usability of the system. Once this stage is complete, a smaller group of participants who experience a visual impairment will be invited to evaluate the system. On a larger scale, the objective is to have the system presented within an exhibit space, welcoming members of the public to the experience in an effort to raise awareness on accessibility.

In an effort to quantify and understand user perceived quality of experience (QoE), explicit, implicit, and objective measures will be captured throughout the experience. With an emphasis on accessibility, a post-experience

questionnaire will be presented to capture an explicit measure of user perceived QoE. Although explicit measures of QoE have remained a cornerstone within experimental evaluations, they can suffer from user bias and memory effects. In this proposal, physiological measures [21] in the form of heart rate, electrodermal activity, blood and volume pulse will be captured using the Empatica E4 [22]. These implicit measures provide opportunity to gain insight into the experience, alleviating challenges such as difficulties with participants articulating the subjective experience accurately. Lastly, as a supportive measure, user interaction within the immersive experience will be captured, these measures aim to support the understanding of physiological measures of QoE [23].

4 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper proposes a multisensory 2.5D VR art exhibition which aims to enhance museum experiences for individuals who are living with a visual impairment. The VR environment allows users to experience visual art by engaging the users sense of touch, smell, and hearing. Users will experience the work of world renown painter Claude Monet within a virtual context. Each virtual painting will present unique sensory zones which will trigger thematic audio and smells, custom haptic feedback, thermal changes, and light and air changes which are unique to the artwork.

As part of future work, a study will be carried out which will capture and report measures of user perceived QoE. The experiment will evaluate two test groups, one with visual impairment and another test group which do not experience any visual impairment. Lastly, in an effort to raise awareness on the topic of accessibility for individuals with visual impairments, it's proposed that the system will be showcased to the public as part of an interactive and immersive arts exhibition.

References

- [1] Museo Nacional del Prado, "Touching the Prado - Exhibition - Museo Nacional del Prado," Museo Nacional del Prado, [Online]. Available: <https://www.museodelprado.es/en/whats-on/exhibition/touching-the-prado/0d94a9bf-07d7-491a-866a-37976169f929>. [Accessed 01 04 2023].
- [2] A. Murphy, "4D exhibition in Netherlands creates sensory experience for sight impaired visitors - MuseumNext," MuseumNext, 20 August 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.museumnext.com/article/4d-exhibition-in-netherlands-creates-sensory-experience-for-sight-impaired-visitors/>. [Accessed 04 April 2023].
- [3] WPP plc, "Geometry Prague: NeuroDigital Touching Masterpieces | WPP," WPP plc, 01 05 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wpp.com/en/featured/work/2019/05/geometry---touching-masterpieces>. [Accessed 25 03 2023].
- [4] Wei Wang; William Yan; Kathy Fotis; Noela M. Prasad; Van Charles Lansingh; Hugh R. Taylor; Robert P. Finger; Damian Facciolo; Mingguang He, "Cataract surgical rate and socioeconomics: A global study," *Clinical and epidemiologic research*, vol. 57, no. 14, pp. 5872- 5881, 2017.
- [5] R. Hajar, "Monet and Cataracts," *Heart Views*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 40-41, 2016.
- [6] C. W. Tyler, "Evidence That Leonardo da Vinci Had Strabismus," *JAMA Ophthalmology*, vol. 137, no. 1, pp. 82-86, 2019.
- [7] A. . B. Safran, N. Sanda and J.-A. Sahel, "A neurological disorder presumably underlies painter Francis Bacon distorted world depiction," *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, vol. 8, no. 581, pp. 1-3, 2014.
- [8] A. Killen, M. J. Firbank, D. Collerton, M. Clarke, J. M. Jefferis, J.-P. Taylor, I. G. McKeith and U. P. Mosimann, "The assessment of cognition in visually impaired older adults," *Age and Ageing*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 98-102, 2013.

- [9] Fever Labs Inc, "Van Gogh Exhibition: The Immersive Experience," Fever Labs Inc, [Online]. Available: <https://vangoghexpo.com/>. [Accessed 15 03 2023].
- [10] Nikoleta Yiannoutsou; Rose Johnson; Sara Price, "Non-visual virtual reality: considerations for the pedagogical design of embodied mathematical experiences for visually impaired children," *Educational Technology & Society*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 151-163, 2021.
- [11] A. N. Moraes, R. Flynn, A. Hines and N. Murray, "The role of physiological responses in a VR-based sound localization task," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 122082-122091, 2021.
- [12] Jun Dong Cho; Jaeho Jeong; Ji Hye Kim; Hoonsuk Lee, "Sound coding colour to improve artwork appreciation by people with visual impairments," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 11, 2020.
- [13] Jorge Iranzo Bartolomé; un Dong Cho; Luis Cavazos Quero; Sunggi Jo; Gilsang Cho, "Thermal interactive for improving tactile artwork depth and colour-depth appreciation for visually impaired people," *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 11, 2020.
- [14] Shaoyu Cai; Pingchuan Ke; Takuji Narumi; Kening Zhu, "ThermAirGlove: A pneumatic glove for thermal perception and material identification in virtual reality," in *Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, Atlanta, 2020.
- [15] Luis Cavazos Quero; Jorge Iranzo Bartolomé; Jundong Cho, "Accessible visual artworks for blind and visually impaired people: Comparing a multimodal approach with tactile graphics," *Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 3, 2021.
- [16] R. R. Brettell, "Monet's Haystacks Reconsidered," *Art Institute of Chicago Museum Studies*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 4-21, 1984.
- [17] E. Provencher, D. Ruddell, "Unity," Unity, 13 March 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://blog.unity.com/engine-platform/whats-new-in-xr-interaction-toolkit-2-3>. [Accessed 22 June 2023].
- [18] M. Meta, "'Prime X Haptic VR,' MANUS Meta," [Online]. Available: <https://www.manus-meta.com/products/prime-x-haptic>. [Accessed 20 03 2023].
- [19] SENSIKS, "'Pod & Platform - SENSIKS,'" [Online]. Available: <https://www.sensiks.com/pods-platform/>. [Accessed 01 04 2023].
- [20] M.T. Paratore, B. Leporini, "Exploiting the haptic and audio channels to improve orientation and mobility apps for the visually impaired," *Universal Access in the Information Society*, pp. 1- 11.
- [21] U. Engelke, D. P. Darcy, G. H. Mulliken, S. Bosse, M. G. Martini, S. Arndt, J.-N. Antons, K. Y. Chat, N. Ramzan and K. Brunnström, "Psychophysiology-Based QoE Assessment: A Survey," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6-21, 2017.
- [22] Empatica, "E4 wristband | Real-time physiological signals | Wearable PPG, EDA, Temperature, Motion sensors," [Online]. Available: <https://www.empatica.com/research/e4/>. [Accessed 05 02 2023].
- [23] C. Keighrey, R. Flynn, S. Murray, S. Brennan and N. Murray, "Comparing User QoE via Physiological and Interaction Measurements of Immersive AR and VR Speech and Language Therapy Applications," in *ACM Multimedia*, Mountain View, CA, USA, 2017.